

A Study to Assess the Effect of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge of Child Safety Among Mothers of Under-Five Children in Selected Rural Community at Durg, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: The current study aimed to assess the effect of structured teaching programme on knowledge of child safety among mothers of under-five children in selected rural community at Durg Chhattisgarh". Quasi-experimental design one group pretest-posttest design is utilized to achieve the stated. **Objectives:** 1. To assess the level of knowledge of mothers of under-five children regarding child safety. 2. To assess the effect of structured teaching programme on knowledge of child safety among mothers of under-five children. 3. To find out the association between the knowledge of mothers regarding child safety with selected demographic variables. **Hypothesis H₁:** There will be a significant difference between the level of knowledge regarding child safety among mothers of under-five children before and after structured teaching programme. **H₂:** There will be a significant association between the pre-test level of knowledge among mothers of under-five with selected socio demographic variables. **Projected Outcome:** In the present study quasi-experimental research design is used to achieve the stated objectives. The study was based on the modified conceptual framework Betty Neuman's system model theory. a quantitative research approach is used and pilot study was conducted to confirm the feasibility of the study. For main study Simple random sampling technique Sample size for this study was 60 mothers of under-five children from rural community Durg Chhattisgarh. The tool used for data collection consists of socio-demographic variables and Questionnaire on knowledge of regarding child safety consist of multiple-choice questions. The data was analyzed using Section I: Description of socio-demographic variables in frequency and percentage. Section II: Analysis of pre and post test score by using mean, mean percentage and standard deviation. Section III: Over all analysis of knowledge score by frequency and percentage. Section IV: t-test to assess the effect of structured teaching programme on knowledge of child safety among mothers of under-five children. Section V: - Chi-square analysis for association of knowledge with selected socio-demographic mean knowledge score regarding knowledge of child safety among rural mothers. the significance of difference in mean knowledge score between pretest and posttest using parametric paired 't' test. Paired 't' test shows Highly significant difference (t=8.94, df=59, P<0.0001) in mean pretest Knowledge score and mean posttest knowledge score knowledge regarding partograph among mothers of under-five children. So, hence, the hypothesis stated that, there will be a significant

difference between the level of knowledge regarding child safety among mothers of under-five children before and after structured teaching programme is accepted. The calculated value of chi square for education were 11.45, df= 4, and the table values 9.49 and chi square for previous knowledge 4.88, df=1, and table value 3.84 were significant.

Keywords: Assess, Knowledge, Structured Teaching Programme, Child Safety, Mothers of under-Five Children, Rural Community.

1. Introduction

Today's Children are the citizens of tomorrow. They deserve to inherit a safer, fairer and healthier world. There is no task more important than safe guarding their environment. Under-five children are proving make sure you fit a safety gate at the top and bottom of stairs and ensure any damaged or worn carpet is repaired or removed to avoid tripping hazards. The future development of our children depends on their enjoying good health today. A house is an exciting place for infants and small children. Who love to explore but aren't aware of the potential dangers. Life can't be risk free, but most of the problems can be prevented by maintaining household safety. The incidence of accidental injuries is increasing in India, especially home accidents in children. The most common injuries are falls, burns, drowning and road accidents and such Injuries commonly occurred in child's own home. In the European region, 3-4 deaths out of 10 that occurred in children between the age of 0 and 4 years. In addition, injuries kill over 20,000 children aged 1-5 every year in the world's wealthiest Nations will die from injuries. The incidence of non-fatal firearm related injuries among children and adolescents treated in US, the estimated annual rates of injuries (per 1,00,000) were 2.0% (children 0-4 years old). Most of the children who fell where between the ages of 0 and 4, all were sent directly to the ICU, 4% of children died. Most window falls occur when children are unsupervised. The distribution of injuries was as follows: falls (50.4%), burns (22.8%), of the 177 falls 104 (58.8%)

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involved stairs, 7 (4%) involved baby walkers, 14 (7.9%) where from changing tables and 1(.6%) was through are open window, the cause was not specified for 51 (28.8%) Of the 80 burn injuries 8 where due to exposure to hot tap water (10%) 27 to hot liquids or solids (33.7%) 22 to hot surfaces (27.5%) and 2 to dwelling fires (2.5%) the cause was not specified for 21 (26.3%). (WHO, 2014).

Fig. 1. Methodology

2. Result and Discussion

The findings of the study were discussed under five sections stated below:

SECTION – I

Findings related to socio-demographic variables:

It shows that 9 (15%) subjects belong to age group of 20-25 years. 25 (41.67%) subjects belong to age group of 25-30 years. 18 (30%) subjects belong to age group of 30-35 years. And 8 (13%) subjects belong to age group of 35-40 years.

It shows that 54 (90%) subjects were Hindu, 1 (1.67%) subjects was Muslim, 4 (6.67%) subjects were Christian, and 1 (1.67%) subject was belongs to other religion she is Shikh, Community.

It shows the maximum 52 (86.67%) subjects belong to Joint family, and 8 (13.33%) subjects belong to Nuclear family.

It shows that 2 (3.33%) subjects were having primary school education, 10 (16.67%) subjects were having middle school education, 23 (38.33%) subjects completed High school education, 17 (28.33%) had higher secondary education, and 8 (13.33%) of there are graduates.

Depicts occupation of mother’s in which 7 (11.67%) are

labour, 48 (80%) are house wives, 2 (3.33%) are doing business, and 3 (5%) working in the office.

It shows that 19 (31.67%) subjects having one child, 36 (60%) subjects are having two children, 5 (8.33%) are having three children.

Depicts that 4 (6.67%) number of family were having four members in their family, 4 (6.67%) number of family were having 5 members in their family, and 52 (86.67%) number of family were having more than five members.

It shows that 9 (15%) subjects were having monthly income less than <5000, The 44 (73.33%) subjects were having monthly income between 5001-10000, The 4 (6.66%) subjects were having monthly income between 10001-15000, and the 3 (5%) subjects were having monthly income above 15000.

It shows that 27(45%) subjects were having the previous knowledge of child safety, and 33 (55%) subjects were not exposed to any education of child safety.

SECTION – II

Analysis of pre-test and post-test knowledge score of structured teaching programme according to criteria

above table shows that before structure teaching programme according to criteria 42 (70%) were having In-adequate knowledge, 18 (30%) were having moderately knowledge, none of there were having adequate knowledge. But after structured teaching programme the knowledge of mothers increased significantly adequate knowledge 15 (25%).

Fig. 2.

SECTION – III

Analysis of pre-test and post-test knowledge score using mean, mean percentage, standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV)

Objective 1: To assess the level of knowledge of mothers of under-five children regarding child safety before structured teaching programme.

Fig. 3.

The fig. 3 shows mean knowledge score regarding knowledge of child safety among rural mothers. Above table shows considerable improvement in posttest mean knowledge score after structured teaching program regarding child safety.

In post-test CV has also reduced to 19.38% from 33.99% in pretest which shows consistency of improved knowledge.

SECTION – IV

Objective 2: Paired ‘t-test’ was used to assess the effective of structured teaching programme on knowledge of child safety among mothers of under-five children.

above table shows the significance of difference in mean knowledge score between pretest and posttest using parametric paired ‘t’ test. Paired ‘t’ test shows Highly significant difference ($t=8.94$, $df=59$, $P<0.0001$) in mean pretest Knowledge score and mean posttest knowledge score knowledge regarding partograph among mothers of under-five children. So, hence, the hypothesis stated that, there will be a significant difference between the level of knowledge regarding child safety among mothers of under-five children before and after structured teaching programme is accepted.

SECTION – V

Chi-square analysis for association between knowledge

It shows the association between knowledge of child safety among mothers of under-five children with their demographic characteristics such as age, income, religion, types of family, education, occupation of mother, number of under-five children in family, family members, income and sources of previous knowledge regarding.

The calculated value of chi square for education were 11.45, $df=4$, and the table values 9.49 and chi square for previous knowledge 4.88, $df=1$, and table value 3.84 were significant.

The calculated value of chi square for age, income, religion, types of family, occupation of mother, number of under-five children in family, family members, monthly income were not significant.

3. Conclusion

In this study, Comparison of overall knowledge score between pre-test and post-test by frequency and percentage. Hence it can be concluded that the planned teaching programme was found good method for achieving knowledge regarding child safety.

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